

A Novel Framework for Multi-Modal Data Integration

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ABSTRACT

Article Info: Received: 08 July 2022 | Accepted: 17 September 2022 | Published online: 07 October 2022

Keywords:

Automatic image annotation has emerged as an important research topic due to its potential application on both image understanding and web image search. This paper presents a model, which integrates visual topics and regional contexts to automatic image annotation. Regional contexts model the relationship between the regions, while visual topics provide the global distribution of topics over an image. Previous image annotation methods neglected the relationship between the regions in an image, while these regions are exactly explanation of the image semantics, therefore considering the relationship between them are helpful to annotate the images. Regional contexts and visual topics are learned by PLSA (Probability Latent Semantic Analysis) from the training data. The proposed model incorporates these two types of information by MCDM (Multi Criteria Decision Making) approach based on WSM (Weighted Sum Method). Experiments conducted on the 5k Corel dataset demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed model.

Automatic Image Annotation, Regional Contexts, Visual Topics, PLSA, Multi Criteria Decision Making

1. INTRODUCTION

With the exponential growth of the Web image, how to retrieval and manage them presents a significant challenge. Content-based Image Retrieval (CBIR) methods compute relevance between images based on the visual similarity of the low-level features [1]-[3]. However, the problem is the so-called “semantic gap” [4] between low-level features and high-level semantic concepts. Therefore, CBIR technique is seldom adopted in practice.

Current commercial image search engines utilize the surrounding textual descriptions of images on the hosting web pages to index web images. These search engines assume the surrounding textual descriptions of images are related to the semantic content of web images. Consequently, the textural descriptions can be used as approximate annotations of web image [3]. On the other hand, the indexing method has many drawbacks. Firstly, there are too many irrelevant words in the surrounding textual descriptions, which results in low image search precision rate. Secondly,

the surrounding text does not seem to fully describe the semantic content of Web images, which results in low image search recall rate. Finally, it cannot be used to retrieval for web images without textual descriptions.

To overcome these shortcomings, Automatic Image Annotation (AIA) has attracted a great deal of attention in recent years.

1.2. Related Works

Existing automatic image annotation methods can be classified into four categories: Vector Space Models [5], [6], Classification Methods [7]-[10], Graph-based Methods [11]-[14] and Statistical Models [15]-[21].

The Vector Space Models: The vector space model [5], [6] framework is a popular technique in information retrieval especially in text retrieval. Generally, documents are represented as vectors, each of which contains the occurrences of keywords within the document in question. The length of the vectors is equal to the vocabulary size. These approaches treat images as documents, and build visual terms which are analogous to keywords, from the image feature descriptors. Some of the methods in this category include: SvdCos method, Saliency-based semantic propagation, and cross-language latent semantic indexing based approach.

Classification Methods: Classification approaches [7]-[10] for image annotation view the process of attaching keywords to images as that of classifying images to a number of pre-defined groups, each of which is characterized by a concept or keyword. These approaches pose image annotation as a supervised classification problem. Specifically, each keyword is viewed as a unique class. Binary classifiers for each class or a multiclass classifier is trained independently to predict the annotations of new images. Given an un-annotated image, the classification algorithms find its membership and annotate it with the corresponding keyword. Multiple annotations can be generated by assuming an image belongs to multiple classes. Some of the works in this category include: image linguistic indexing, image annotation using SVM, multiple instance learning approaches, non-negative Matrix factorization based approaches.

Graph Based Methods: Recently, the graph-based methods [11]-[14] have achieved much success in the image and video analysis domain including image annotation. How to build a similarity graph is very important in graph learning. A good graph should reflect a deep understanding of the data structure and help to mine potential knowledge as much as possible. Some works in this category include: image annotation via graph learning, image annotation refinement via graph based learning.

Statistical Models: The basic idea of statistical techniques [15]-[21] is to estimate the probabilities of documents related to the query submitted by the user. Documents are then ranked according to their probabilities. The main goal of statistical techniques is to learn a model from the joint distribution of visual and textual features on the training data and predicting the missing textual features for a new image.

Among the image annotation models classification approaches are the oldest in this domain. But statistical models and graph based approaches have more chance. The proposed approach in this paper follows statistical based models. So we will review the statistical models that are proposed for automatic image annotation.

The co-occurrence model proposed by Mori et al. [16] is perhaps one of the first attempts at automatic image annotation. They first divide images into rectangular tiles of the same size, and calculate a feature descriptor of color and texture for each tile. All the descriptors are clustered into a number of groups, each of which is represented by the centroid. Each tile inherits the whole set of labels from the original image. Then, they estimate the probability of a keyword W related to a cluster C by the co-occurrence of the keyword and the image tiles within the cluster.

Duygulu et al. [17] proposed a machine translation model for automatic image annotation. They argued that region based image annotation is more interesting because global annotation does not give information on which part of the image is related to which keyword. In their point of view, the process of attaching keywords to image regions is analogous to the translation of one form of representation (image regions; French) to another form (words; English). Indeed, Their Machine translation model applies one of the classical statistical machine translation models to translate from the set of keywords of an image to the set of blobs that generated by clustering the image features.

Jeon et al. [18] proposed Cross Media Relevance Model (CMRM) for automatic image annotation. CMRM benefits the joint distribution of keywords and blobs. Each image describe by visual features (blobs) as well as textual keywords. In CMRM the probability of observing a set of blobs with a set of keywords estimated.

Lavrenko et al. [19] proposed a Continues-space Relevance Model (CRM) that improves CMRM by using continuous probability density functions to estimate the probability of observing a region given an image.

(MBRM) such that the probability of observing labels given an image was modeled as a multipleBernoulli distribution. In MBRM images simply divided into rectangular tiles instead of applying automatic segmentation algorithms.

There exist two problems in above algorithms. First, most existing algorithms have taken one of two approaches, using regional or global features exclusively. Second, conventional approaches consider each word separately without the textual context relations. As a result the textual context relations among annotation words have been ignored. By textual context we refer to cooccurrence relationship among words. Wang et al. [21] proposed a model for image annotation that combines global, regional, and contextual features by an extended CMRM. They incorporate the three kinds of information to describe image semantics to annotate images by estimating their joint probability.

1.2. Our Approach

There exists an important problem in all of the statistical methods, that all the explained methods utilize direct distribution of regions for AIA. However considering the relationship between regions, that each of them is an explanation of a word, helps us to improve the final annotation words. So we obtain the relationship between regions and instead of using the direct distribution of regions, we utilize the distribution of topics between regions for AIA.

To address the above problem we propose a novel approach for AIA. Typical CMRM only takes regional features to describe an image, the extended CMRM incorporates both global and regional features, as well as textual context to annotate images. In the approach that we propose, the *visual topics* have described as a global distribution vector of topics in the image, moreover we consider the obtained relationship between regions and model the *regional contexts* as a distribution of topics between regions. Both the visual topics and regional contexts are learned by a PLSA approach [22] from the training data. Then we integrate these two kinds of information by MCDM approach based on WSM. Generally our method includes three steps as follows:

1. Model the regional contexts or the relationship between the regions as a distribution of topics between regions for generating the annotation related to image regions content.
2. Utilize the visual topics as a global distribution vector of topics to consider the overall image content.
3. Combining the extracted two kinds of information from the image using the WSM in MCDM algorithm.

The framework is shown in Fig. 1. The images are represented by their regions and collection of patches. Our proposed model is learned from the training data based on the two kinds of information, regional contexts $BI()$ and visual topics $HI()$.

1.3. Paper Outline

The reminder of this paper organized as follows: Extended CMRM is described in section 2. Our proposed model is introduced in section 3. In section 4 experimental results are presented and finally concluding remarks are explained in section 5.

2. EXTENDED CMRM

The conventional CMRM [18] considers only one representation of images, i.e. a bag of blobs. To deal with images which are not suitable to be represented as a bag of blobs, we need to consider other representation as well. So, ECMRM [21] has proposed to use visual topics as another representation. This new image representation is combined with the visual blobs representation. Moreover the typical CMRM annotates keywords individually without considering the joint distribution of different keywords. To solve this problem, textual context is proposed. To annotate

an image with multiple keywords, first annotate the image with textual contexts and then compose the keywords from the distribution of keywords under each textual context. The learning of textual context is based on the PLSA approach [22]. PLSA is proposed to automatically learn topics from text documents. Similar to learn topics from text documents, we can also learn visual topics from images.

The ECMRM method annotates a test image I by estimating the joint probability of textual contexts C , its visual blobs (regions) $R=(b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m)$ obtained by image segmentation [23] and the visual topics distribution $H(I)$, which J represents training image and τ is the training set:

$$P(C, R, H(I) | J) = \sum_{C \in \tau} P(C) P(R | C) P(H(I) | C, R) \tag{1}$$

Comparing ECMRM with CMRM, there are two points of difference to elaborate. First, the original CMRM in annotates an image using only the regional features $R=(b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m)$. However, ECMRM uses both the regional features R and the global features $H(I)$ which represent the global distribution of visual topics in image I . This suggests the ECMRM model combines the global features and regional features. Second, CMRM predicts the probability of a single word W directly, while ECMRM predicts the probability of a textual context C . This indicates ECMRM does not assume the mutual independence between words given the image. Thus, the extended CMRM incorporates the textual context from the training data.

Textual contexts C , image blobs and visual topics distribution are independent. So that

$$P(C, R, H(I) | J) \text{ can be simplified as:} \tag{2}$$

$$P(C, R, H(I) | J) = P(C) P(R | C) P(H(I) | C, R) = P(C) \prod_{i=1}^m P(b_i | C) P(H(I) | C, R) \tag{2}$$

$P(b_i | C)$ is estimated as the same as that in CMRM. $P(C | I)$ is available after learning textual

contexts on the manual annotations. $D_{kl}(P(I|J) || P(J))$ is defined as the Kullback-Leibler divergence between the visual topic distribution of I and J :

Figure 1. The proposed approach to automatic image annotation using regional contexts and visual topics.

$$D_{kl}(P(H|I) || P(H|J)) = \sum_{i=1}^Q \frac{P_q I(i)}{P_q J(i)} \log \left(\frac{P_q I(i)}{P_q J(i)} \right) \tag{3}$$

In which D_{kl} is the Kullback-Leibler divergence between two distributions. From the Bayesian theory, we know that:

$$P_C I(i) = P_C I(i, \dots) = P_C b(i, \dots, b_m, H I(i)) \tag{4}$$

Therefore, normalization on $P_C b(i, \dots, b_m, H I(i))$ will give the conditional distribution of textual contexts $P_C I(i)$. The conditional keyword distribution $P_W I(j)$ of I is obtained by fusing the keyword distribution of the entire textual contexts:

S

$$P W I(j) = \sum_i P W C P C I(j_i) (i) \quad (5)$$

3.The Proposed Scheme

The notable point is that the relationship between regions is not considered in the ECMRM method. We know that each of these regions is explanation of a word and the semantic relationship between these regions is more accurate than the semantic relationship between words (textual contexts), which are assigned to the image by human. Because these regions have represented the exact content of an image, finally the generated keywords are related to the image content.

3.1.Learning Regional Contexts from Images

Similar to learning topics from text document in the ECMRM method, we can also learn regional contexts from a collection of images. Firstly, according to ECMRM method the regions are obtained from image segmentation based on objects [23]. We should represent an image as a collection of words, so consider an image as a document and assume the objects in an image as words in this document (we consider each region as a word). Then apply the PLSA approach developed by Hoffman to reach the relationship between regions and instead of the direct distribution of regions in an ECMRM, we utilize the distribution of topics between them to AIA. We call these topics, which have described the relationship between regions, regional context.

PLSA approach [22] behaves as follows:

Suppose we are given a set of text documents $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n\}$ each of which is represented by a term frequency vector:

$$d_i = (n d w(i, 1), n d w(i, 2), \dots, n d w(i, m)) \quad (6)$$

In which $n d w(i, j)$ is the number of occurrence of word w_j in document d_i , and m is the vocabulary size. PLSA assumes that each word in a document is generated by a specific hidden topic Z_k , where $Z_k \in I$ and I is the vocabulary of hidden topics. Since Z_k is a hidden variable, the conditional probability of a word w_j given document d_i is a marginalization over the topics:

$$P W d(j_i) = \sum_k P W Z d(j_k, i) (k_i) \quad (7)$$

In which K is the number of hidden topics, $P W Z d(j_k, i)$ is the conditional probability of a word w_j given topic Z_k and the document d_i , $P Z d(k_i)$ is the conditional probability of topic Z_k given d_i .

Furthermore, PLSA assumes that the conditional probability of generating a word by a specific topic is independent from the document:

$$P_{w|z} d(jk, i) = P_{w|z} (jk) \quad (8)$$

Therefore (7) can be simplified as:

$$P_{w|d} (ji) = \sum_k^K P_{w|z} P_{z|d} (jk) (ki) \quad (9)$$

The model parameters $P_{w|z} (jk)$ and $P_{z|d} (ki)$ can be learned by an EM algorithm [24].

3.2. Learning Visual Topics from Images

Similar to learning topics from text documents, we can also learn visual topics from images. The notable point is representing an image as a bag of words [25], like to the vector representation of text documents. We partition an image by a regular grid and take it as an unordered set of image patches. Then we extract a Gabor descriptor [26]-[28] and vector quantizes each image patch by clustering a subset of patches from the training images, which has proved effective for object recognition [28]. Therefore, we develop the orientation histogram [29] from multi-scale Gabor features because Gabor features are better representation than simple gradient features. We call the cluster centers as visual words. Then we can transform an image into a bag of visual words by assigning a visual word label to each image patch. We have the bag of visual word representation, apply the PLSA to learn a set of visual topics.

There is a difference between image regions obtained by image segmentation and image patches. Image patches that grouped in a topic do not have spatial agglomeration and visual consistency although image segmentation groups pixels by its visual property and spatial location. Fig. 2 illustrates the image regions, image patches and the distributions of regional context and visual topics of an image. Visual topics and regional contexts (topics between regions obtained by image segmentation) focus on different aspect of an image, so they are complementary to each other and a combination of them is expected to achieve better performance.

Figure 2. Illustration of two types of information: (A) Original image, (B) Image regions have obtained by segmentation, (C) Distribution of regional contexts, (D) Image patches that the patches with the same topic are indicated by the same color, (E) Distribution of visual topics

3.3. Combining Regional Contexts and Visual Topics

Our method annotates a test image I by combining the regional contexts (the distribution of topics between regions) $B I ()$ and the visual topics distribution $H I ()$ and considering a given word (W):

$$P W B I H I (, () , ()) = \sum_{J \in \tau} P J P W B I () (, () , H I J ()) \tag{10}$$

Comparing (10) with (1) there is one point of difference to elaborate: ECMRM in (1) annotates an image uses both the regional features R and the global features $H I ()$, means that it uses the direct distribution of regions. But our method in (10) considers to the relationship between the regions and it uses the distribution of topics between regions as a regional contexts $B I ()$. Because the semantic relationship between regions is more accurate than the relationship between words, we have ignored the textual context in (1) and instead of it we utilize regional contexts. So we utilize both the regional contexts and visual topics together. These two kinds of information extract different words, so combining them are useful to create related words and consistent to image content.

However the conventional methods suppose the conditionally independence between the regional information and visual words, but we cannot consider this assumption. It is obvious that to obtain the regional information we cannot utilize the image directly and we should use the image features domain. Subsequently regional information is dependent to the visual words, because the visual words are in this domain too. This dependency stems from that one of the important extracted features from the image needed for regional representation is texture which cannot be independent from the visual words.

To solve this problem we explain the distribution of test image keywords generally as below equation:

$$p_w(I) = \sum_{J \in \tau} p_w(J) \alpha_j \quad (11)$$

This equation is similar to (10), but we utilize α_j instead of considering the distribution of $B I()$ and $H I()$. According to (11) the annotation of a test image is equal to the sum of multiply the distribution of training image keywords in their coefficient (α_j). This coefficient calculates the similarity of a test image I with the training images, considering to (10) in our proposed model α_j is the conditional joint distribution of the regional contexts and visual topics. Indeed α_j define the contribution of training image keywords to create the distribution of test image keywords. We can understand easily that if one training image is more similar to the test image I , the distribution of their keywords is similar too, and the contribution of that training image or α_j should be more. As regards $B I()$ and $H I()$ are dependent and to simplify (10) and calculate α_j or the similarity between the test image and training images we use the MCDM (Multi Criteria Decision Making) approach. MCDM is the selection of the best action from a set of alternatives, each of which is evaluated against multiple criteria.

Among the MCDM methods, we utilize the WSM (Weighted Sum Method).

Inputs to WSM methods are as follows:

- WSM assumes that we have N alternatives (options) and M attributes (criteria) and we have the score of each option with respect to each criterion. In our model the alternatives are training images and the criteria are regional contexts and visual topics. Indeed to determine the criteria we should introduce some measure to calculate the similarity. We obtain these measures by investigating the various experimental results. In the different experiment, we fetch up that α_j and α_j increase the precision and $\alpha_j * \alpha_j$ has an influence to boost the recall, so we specify these measures:

$$\left(\frac{PBIJ(I)}{PBIJ(J)} \right)^2, PBIJ(I), PBIJ(J), PHIJ(I) \quad (12)$$

- Let x_{ij} score of option i with respect to criterion j , we have the $m \times n$ matrix. Then we construct normalized decision matrix. This step transforms various attribute dimensions into non-dimensional attributes, which allows comparisons across criteria. r_{ij} is the normalized rating of the of the i^{th} alternative for the j^{th} criterion.
- Construct the weighted normalized decision matrix. Assume we have a set of weights for each criterion w_j for $j=1, \dots, n$. These weights express the relative importance of it in respect to the others. Considering the 3 suggested criteria in our model, we need to define 3 weights for them:

$$w_1 = \frac{a}{a+7}, w_2 = \frac{1-a}{7} \quad (13)$$

- Calculate the S_i , S_i is the overall score of i^{th} alternative.

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^M w_j r_{ij} \quad \text{for } i=1, 2, \dots, N \quad (14)$$

Note that in this method the alternative with the highest score is selected as the preferred one. Considering to the suggested criteria, we need to calculate the $PBIJ(I)$ and $PHIJ(I)$. These two items are defined as the Kullback-Leibler divergence between the distribution image I and image J , according to (3) $PHIJ(I)$ is available:

$$PBIJ(I) = D_{kl}(PBIJ(I) || PHIJ(I)) = \sum_{i=1}^Q \frac{P_q(I)}{PHIJ(I)} \log \left(\frac{P_q(I)}{PHIJ(I)} \right) \quad (15)$$

4.Experimental Results and Discussion

In this section we will discuss details of the dataset and also show experimental results. The test bed and evaluation metrics are introduced in Section 4.1 and Section 4.2, respectively. The experimental results with compared to other annotation models are presented in Section 4.3.

4.1. Test Bed

We have used a set of Corel images consists of 5000 images to evaluate the proposed model. The image database consists of 50 main topics and each class includes 100 images. COREL-5K was first collected by Duygulu et al. [17] and it has been extensively used by other researchers, so it has been known as a de facto standard dataset in image annotation researches. Each image is also associated with 1-5 keywords. Therefore, there are 374 keywords in the dataset.

We partition the whole data set into a training set and a test set, 4500 training images and 500 test images. For the region features, we use the JSEG algorithm [23] to segment each image into 1-11 regions. Image regions with area less than 1/25 of the whole image are discarded. In average there are five image regions per image. Each image region is represented by a 36-D feature vector. For the dense grid, we sample 13×13 pixels image patches without overlapping. The average number of image patches per image is around 550. The image regions are clustered into 500 image blobs, similarly the Gabor descriptor of image patches are clustered into 500 centered. We experiment on different number of visual topics (I), textual context (T) and regional contexts (R) and achieve the best number of them that are shown in results.

4.2. Evaluation Metrics

For each method, we take the top five words as the final annotation. We use precision, recall and F_1 metrics, to evaluate the quality of our approach. Precision and recall are calculated on the basis of each keyword in the vocabulary. Then the values are averaged over the keywords in the vocabulary.

Precision is defined as the number of images correctly predicted with a given keyword called r , divided by the total number of images predicted with the keyword called n . Recall is defined as the number of images correctly predicted with a given keyword, divided by the total number of images having this keyword in its ground-truth called N .

$$\text{Precision } W(\quad) = \frac{r}{n} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Recall } W(\quad) = \frac{r}{N} \quad (17)$$

$$F_1 = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{(\text{Precision} + \text{Recall})} \quad (18)$$

We also use keyword number with recall > 0 to show the diversity of correct words that can be predicted by the automatic image annotation model. The measure is important because a model can achieve high precision and recall values by only performing well on a small number of common words.

4.3. Comparative Analysis

The results of experiments are shown in Table 1. Comparing the results in a table, the improvement of ECMRM [21] which incorporates the regional, global and contextual features to original CMRM [18] is obvious and improved F_1 value from 0.1115 to 0.3270. But in the proposed approach, we combine the regional contexts and visual topics, which has achieved the best performance and improved F_1 value from 0.3270 to 0.4665. In addition precision, recall and keyword number with recall>0 measure have been significantly improved. In summary using the regional contexts (neglect the textual context), significantly improve the performance, because the regions or objects in an image are exactly the explanation of image content. Also each of these regions acts as one word, so the relationship between the regions is more accurate than textual contexts to create annotation keywords. Textual contexts have some noises, because the keywords of training images are created manually and by human, consequently they have inconsistency. It is obvious that incorporating this information with visual topics help us to achieve the best performance, because these two kinds of information focus on different aspects of an image, extract different words and they are complementary to each other. Fig. 3 shows F_1 value of sample words in CMRM, ECMRM and the proposed approach. The difference between the F_1 value of our method and ECMRM of sample words in Fig. 3 shows the noises in the manual annotation and textual contexts of ECMRM method. We can observe that considering the relationship between regions is helpful to obtain the annotation keywords related to image content and increase the F_1 value. Some test images with the annotations generated by the CMRM, ECMRM and the proposed approach are demonstrated in Fig. 4. It is observed that the proposed approach can yield better annotations, which describe image semantics, than ECMRM.

Table 1. The average precision, recall, F_1 and keywords with recall>0 values of experiments

Models	CMRM [18]	ECMRM [21]	The Proposed Approach
Precision	0.1288	0.3050	0.4942
Recall	0.0983	0.3524	0.4417
F_1	0.1115	0.3270	0.4665
Keywords with recall>0			

Figure 3. Some sample words and their F_1 value in CMRM, ECMRM and the proposed approach

Image						
Ground Truth	Clouds, Sea, Sun, Tree	Gate, Grass, Temple, Tree	Cars, Formula, Tracks, Wall	Jet, Mountain, Plane	Bear, Polar, Snow, Tundra	Cat, Forest, Grass, Tiger
CMRM	Buildings, Sunset, Skyline, City, Water	People, Buildings, Flag, Parade, Sky	People, Water, Cars, Tree, Sky	Sky, Plane, Jet, Birds, Albatross	Water, Sky, Bear, Tree, Plane	Water, Tree, Grass, Garden, Plants
ECMRM	Buildings, Sunset, Water, People, Skyline	Water, Sky, People, Buildings, Boats	People, Cars, Water, Tracks, Street	Sky, Plane, Jet, Birds, People	Bear, Polar, Tree, Water, Snow	Grass, Plants, Cat, Garden, Tree
Proposed Approach	Water, Tree, Sky, Sunset, Skyline	Grass, Tree, Temple, Sky, People	Cars, People, Tracks, Street, Race	Sky, Plane, Jet, Tree, Clouds	Bear, Polar, Snow, Ice, Water	Cat, Grass, Plants, Forest, Garden

Figure 4. Some sample words and their F_1 value in CMRM, ECMRM and the proposed approach

5.CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have proposed a method for AIA which is improved the result of ECMRM method. Instead of using the direct distribution of regions in ECMRM, we utilize the distribution of topics between regions. Moreover regional contexts are more accurate than textual contexts or the relationship between keywords in ECMRM. The proposed approach combines the regional contexts and visual topics for automatic image annotation, as for the dependence between these two kinds of information in the image, we use the MCDM approach based on WSM to integrate them. To obtain global distribution of topics, visual topics are learned from the training images by a PLSA approach. Furthermore, PLSA has used to model the regional contexts or the topics between regions. The proposed method is tested on a 5000 Corel data set and the results show that utilization of regional contexts or considering the relationship between regions improves the performance significantly and its incorporation with the visual topics leads to the best performance.

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Journal of Functional Materials

Peer-Reviewed | Open Access | ISSN: 1001-9731 | Vol 30, Issue 10 (2022)

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